

The Social Dimension of Mass Media in Iraq

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Abstract: The present study aims to explore the study of media language of Iraq from the linguistic power perspective in terms of its social dimensions. Media plays a very important role in shaping the attitudes and opinions of the people towards social, political and economic situations. The objective of the study is to study two types of media discourse, namely English and Arabic news, and editorials broadcasted in Iraq.

The mentioned two media discourse are discussed and analyzed through constructive analysis from social dimension. The paper reviews the literature on media and communication; regarding that, Hohenberg (1969) mentions that the meaning of the news intended to convey to the public needs to be clear. Schramm (1973) focuses on the human communication and its nature in terms of social standpoint. The paper also discusses the literature on language of media. Karam (1986) mentions that from the communicative function perspective, the message is significant as it is conveyed to the society in general through language.

The book of Stuart, H. Et al. (1972) titled as Culture, Media and Language has made a significant contribution to the study of media language by highlighting the relationship between the development of language of media and social change. In addition, the paper also deliberates on literature related to media discourse analysis and discourse analysis theory. Emam (1969) proclaims that the writers who write for newspaper editorial should have broad cultural, historical and social backgrounds. Labov (1970) has claimed that style shifting is connected with some linguistic variables as the social context and topic change significantly.

Discourse analysis theory has been adopted to base the theoretical framework of this study. The research design of the study follows the qualitative method. The findings of the study show that the social aspect of the media language in Iraq has not been seriously treated or considered. Thus, the present research makes an attempt to analyze and discuss the dimension that characterizes the media language in Iraq.

INTRODUCTION

The social dimension of human language is severely important for the linguistic power. The study of human language will be meaningless without studying its social context dimension because human language is used for

communicating among individuals in society. So, human language has a social message conveyed through humans depending on the context language is used in. Our concern here is the media language which will be studied in light of its linguistic power from social point of view.

Media language has a very important role in influencing people's attitudes and opinions towards certain political, economic and social issues, this is due to the fact that media language has a social role, in which it conveys a social message for all individuals in the society. So, media language has a social dimension based on to whom the writer directs his speech and how he/she reflects it through the language he uses.

1.1 Background of the Study

The human language and its study of social dimension are very significant for linguistic power. If we study any human language, we need to study the social context since human language is used for communicating among individuals in society. Human language has a social message, and it depends on the context where language is used. Media language plays a very vital role in shaping people's opinion and attitude towards social, political and economic issues. The present study aims to study media language and its linguistic power from a social standpoint. The study makes an attempt to explore the mentioned dimension in order to find out its influence in shaping the media language of Iraq.

For that, the present study discusses and analyzes the English and Arabic newspaper editorials and the English and Arabic news broadcast through a contrastive analysis, considering the social dimension. In order to account the study and its exploration, the paper incorporates a multidisciplinary approach to the study of newspapers' editorial and news broadcasts. Under the qualitative method, discourse analysis theory has been put forward to base the framework of this study.

The present study wants to notice whether the socio-dimension of the media language of Iraq has not been seriously tackled or treated. Thus, the present research attempts to analyze and discuss this dimension that characterize the media language in Iraq. The paper also aims to explore that the mentioned editorials and news broadcasts have undergone a linguistic analysis from a social point of view.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Linguists argue that media language has a social dimension. This dimension is the main reason for the change in the mass media discourse from one language to another. This study is an attempt to study this dimension in order to find out its influence in shaping the media language of Iraq.

The concern of the research is, thus, to discuss and analyze the English and Arabic newspaper editorials and the English and Arabic news broadcast through a contrastive analysis of the social dimension for these two types of media

discourse. However, the researcher believes that this study will open the door wide for further studies on the mass media language in Iraq.

1.3 Research questions

1. What are the ways can be followed to obtain the general social standpoints related to the language of mass media in Iraq?
2. What are the factors responsible for affecting the people to have a better understanding on the part of specialists and journalists considering the social aspect of the mass media?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The study makes an attempt to explore the following objectives:

1. To identify the structure of the general social dimension of the mass media language in Iraq.
2. To find out the point of view of the newspaper editorials and news broadcast from the social angle in order to enhance the understanding of the specialists and journalists which will reflect the social aspect of the mass media of Iraq.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The present study is significant in its own because it is the first study, which emphasizes and highlights the social aspects of the mass media language of Iraq. In addition, the study also makes a significant contribution to the other researchers who are keen to do a search on the language of mass media in Iraq. Secondly, this study also incorporates a multi-disciplinary approach in order to investigate newspaper editorials and news broadcast. The present study also employs manifold aspects of various disciplines, such as, sociolinguistics, , journalism, media discourse and linguistic discourse Analysis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Literature in Media and Communication

The first study to mention is that of Bradley (1967) which has tackled the development of newspapers in America. The study shows how the American newspapers influence the American's ideas and thoughts and how these newspapers reflect the social changes in the American society. Besides, the study focuses on the role of newspaper editorials in reflecting the editor's opinions for the public and the role of newspapers in the American society as a helping device for the readers to find the truth. So, the significance of this study stems from its emphasis on the role of newspapers and editorials in reflecting the American society, its values, opinions and democracy.

In a book entitled *The Professional Journalist*, Hohenberg (1969) has discussed the work of a journalist and his principal tools, such as: language, method and

other fundamental procedures. The researcher thinks that the editor should know the people's interest and their knowledge is he wants to be a successful editor. He also focuses on the idea that the meaning of the news should be clear to the public. He defines news as "any event, idea, or opinion that is timely, that interests or affects a large number of people in a community, and that is capable of being understood by them" (p. 78).

Schramm (1973) has focused on the nature of human communication from psychological and social aspects. He reviews several theories related to the relationship among media, communication and society.

In this study, the researcher defines communication as "the process that allows us to form the images in our heads that map our environment and guide our behavior" (p. 10). Besides, he discusses the effect of communication that is based on a cognitive basis through reviewing different theories on the "group communication".

Eco (1976) has conducted a study of the theory of semiotics that aims at exploring the social function of the semiotic approach to every phenomenon of signification and communication. Eco also claims that mass communication can be studied from a semiotic perspective on the basis of studying the transmission of messages between the addresser and the addressee.

However, the researcher concludes that "the analysis of mass communication is considered as one sector of a general semiotics and it should be studied in the light of methods ranging from psychology and sociology and stylistics" (p. 13).

In their book entitled *Culture, Society, and the Media* (1977), Curran, J. Et al. Have discussed two related themes concerning the role and processes of mass communication in society. The first deals with questions regarding the power of the media: how should it be defined? How is it wielded, and by whom? The second theme revolves around the division between liberal pluralist and the Marxist approaches to the analysis of the nature of the media.

Casebier, A. And Casebier J. (1978) have tackled the social responsibilities of the mass media. This study attempts to discuss the rights and obligations of those responsible for mass media news and entertainment. Friske and Hartley (1978) have conducted a study on the role of television in society. They try to combine a theory of the cultural role of television with a semiotic-based method of analysis whereby an individual broadcast item can be critically read. The study also pushes the boundaries of television studies beyond the insight offered by sociology and psychology into those offered by cultural studies and textual analysis.

Johnston (1979) has conducted a distinguished study entitled *Journalism and the Media*. This study aims at studying the types of media and their functions in society. It also describes the technique used by journalists to gather, write, and present.

In a book entitled *Introduction to communication Studies*, Friske (1982) has introduced the main approach to the study of communication. This book aims to equip the reader with a range of methods of analyzing examples of communication in society, together with a critical awareness of the theories underpinning them. Besides, the book also draws upon the main authorities in the field, from Shannon and Weaver's Communication theory to Saussure's structural linguistics and Peirce's Semiotics.

The last study to mention in this section is that of Rai (1992) which has discussed the basic nature of journalism. In this study, the researcher specifies the necessary steps to become a successful journalist. The most important of these is that the journalist has to have some breadth of culture, knowledge of society and its values, knowledge of language to influence the society, and knowledge of the world events.

2.2 Literature on Media, Language

Karam (1986) discusses the relationship between language and media in regard to the communicative function of both language and media. He claims that the message is the most important element in the communicative function which is conveyed to the society through language.

In their book entitled, *Culture, Media, and language*, Stuart, H. Et al. (1972) have discussed media language from many perspectives. They claim that the media have an ideological role which is related to its social and cultural roles. This book has made a very important contribution to the study of media language. It sheds light on the relationship between the development of media language and the social change which is very important in understanding the great influence of society on the media language.

Mohammad (1984) has conducted a study on the relationship between language and media. He claims that the relationship between media and language lies in the study of semantics. The researcher also discusses that linguists are concerned with the study of the semantic aspects of language, whereas the persons working in the media field are concerned with the relationship between the addresser and the addressee in conveying the media message.

Teun A. Van Dijk (1985) has made a very valuable contribution to the study of media language. He focuses on the study of media language from several theoretical perspectives. In this study, the socio-cultural and socio-psycho perspectives give much account. He claims that media message should be viewed from its socio-cultural, socio-psychological and socio-political dimensions.

Sharaf (1989) distinguishes between the broad sense of the language and the language in the media context. He claims that language is an abstract means of communication, but when it is related to the media, it acquires its social dimension to become a tool of reflecting the society.

The last study to mention that has in this section is that of Jawad (1998) that has contributed to the study of media language through dealing with the press language in its social and cultural context. He also claims that the language reflects the social and cultural developments in society.

2.3 Literature on Media Discourse Analysis

Emam (1969) has conducted a study that aims at studying the art of journalistic editing. He claims that the writer of the newspaper editorial should have broad cultural, historical and social backgrounds. He should also have a special journalistic talent to enable him to criticize the current events in a subjective method.

Most of the argumentative style of editorial texts is based on a persuasive strategy. Barker (1978) argues that persuasion is a deliberate attempt by one person to modify attitudes, beliefs, or behavior of another person or group of people by transmitting a message. Also, Barker indicates that there are three degrees of persuasion that can vary, a speaker who intend to persuade may convince, stimulate, or move the audience by action.

Harthly (1982) has conducted a study on understanding news. He claims that television news is the point of contact between people and politics, between the home and the public world of debate and decision. So, this study shows how news is constructed, not as a product so much as a "language" of meanings, values, codes, and convictions by which we as consumers are encouraged to make sense of the world.

Van Dijk (1983) has analyzed media discourse in terms of several theoretical perspectives. The first perspective is "functionality" which relates to the structures and meanings expressed in discourse that several information about the relationship between the participants (i.e. The writer and the reader) and about the social situation. This functional aspect is important because "news is not simply as (complete) description of facts, but a specific kind of (re) construction of reality according to the norms and values of some society" (p. 28).

The second perspective is the "cognitive expectations". In this perspective, Van Dijk argues that news events are not directly presented, since reporters are usually indirect witnesses to the events; the data most often from other discourse. Hence, the news goes through several stages before it is in a final form. These stages are the cognitive operations of the journalists and the readers. Consequently, understanding the news involves going beyond the surface structures and into presuppositions and interpretations. In other terms, "the structure of news is ultimately the one assigned to the text by the reader" (P.29).

The last perspective is the stylistic structures" whose importance stems from the fact that they reveal social and cognitive functions of language choice, and they also bear upon the level of formality of newspapers.

Concerning the importance of argumentative discourse in media discourse, Tirkkonen-Condit (1985) has conducted a study that aims at studying argumentative discourse. They claim that a text is argumentative when it expresses an opinion and when it contains quality-attributing statements.

Shunnaq (1986) has tackled the language of newspapers from a stylistic point of view. The researcher claims that the language of newspapers varies according to the context and situation which reflects their effect on the type of text. Shunnaq has also tackled the language of broadcasting, where he focuses on the formal style of broadcast language. He thinks that the new language has different styles according to the status of the audience. Therefore, this study attempts to explain the relationship between the style of newspaper and news languages and the status of audiences, which has its great influence on the style of newspaper and news languages.

Abdalnaby (1989) has conducted a study that aims at studying the social dimension of the journalistic news and the news values in the Egyptian newspapers. The researcher also discusses the role of subjectivity in the news editing. Besides, he elaborates on the role of press institution policy, the nature of the political regime and the socio-economical dimension of the society in the editing of the news.

One of the most important books in the field of media discourse is that of Fairclough's, entitled *Media Discourse* (1995). In this book, he claims that the analysis of media texts should be mapped onto analysis of the institutional and wider social and cultural context of media practices, including relations of power and ideologies of society. Fairclough attempts to convince the readers that the analysis of media discourse should be recognized as an important element within research on contemporary processes of social and cultural change. It is quite obvious that the study attempts to deal with media discourse in its social and cultural context through theoretical view in this field.

Al-Hammed (1999) has made a contribution to the study of political discourse analysis through highlighting some of the linguistic features in political discourse in the Arabic language. The researcher comments on the socio-political discourse by arguing that this type of discourse addresses the society in its different conditions, it also discusses the social conditions and the differences between the classes in the society.

Besides, the researcher discusses the essence of mass-media discourse through saying that this kind of discourse presents the political news, analyses them or elaborates on them. However, Al-Hammed assures that political discourse adopt the view of government that takes this factor into account because through this factor the government can influence the people's opinions and direct their views or warm up them against certain unacceptable opinion either explicitly or implicitly.

Thetela (2001), in his article "Critique Discourse and Ideology in Newspaper Reports", has described the role of ideologies in the news language. He thinks that news texts are social practices (i.e. they represent the view and actions of certain social classes or groups); he also claims that the analysis of news reports is mainly based on the framework of ideology which has the cognitive function of organizing the social representation of the group and related social practices, and hence the text and talk of its members. Thus, this study focuses on the ideology of the society and its role in influencing the news language.

Van Dijk (2001a) attempts to shed light on general properties of ideologies as forms of social, cognitive and their relation to political text. The Dijk's study aims at answering the question whether specific discourse genres or domains, such as those of politics, have specific ways of formulating ideology. The researcher defines ideologies as "the basis of the social representations of groups" (p. 1). Besides, he differentiates between two kinds of ideologies: "professional ideologies" that underlay their functioning as politicians and "the socio-political ideologies" that the politicians are adhered to, e.g. as members of political parties or social groups.

2.4 Literature on Discourse Analysis Theory

This section is limited to those studies that touch upon the discourse analysis theory from its sociolinguistic and psycholinguistic aspects. Even within these limits, however, diverse concepts and dimensions must be considered. The purpose of this section is to contribute to analyze the media the media discourse in the context of discourse analysis theories which will help the researcher understand the linguistic dimensions of media discourse from an analytic point of view.

The first study to mention is that of Morris (1969) which has defined a genre as "a category of art distinguished by a definite style, form, or content" (p.550). Guiraud (1974) says that genre determines the form and content of an expression. According to him, a theory of genres belongs to functional stylistics in that it is a classification of texts according to their function and media adapted to these functions.

In an article entitled "The Study of Language in its Social Context", Labov (1970) has claimed that style shifting is related to some linguistic variables as the social context and topic change. He also thinks that some of these shifts in style "can be detected qualitatively in the minor self-corrections of the speaker, which are almost always in uniform direction" (p.180).

Fairclough (1992) studies, social change in the discourse theory. The researcher claims that changes in language use are linked to wider social and cultural processes. He also develops an approach to language analysis which will be particularly useful for investigating changes in language, and will be usable in studies of social and cultural change. Fairclough argues that the mass media are shifting the boundary between the public and private spheres of social life.

Besides, he describes briefly a number of recent and current approaches to discourse analysis in order to combine close analysis of language texts with a social orientation to discourse.

Beaugrand (1995) has conducted a study of the theory of text and discourse in the light of the cognitive processes which relate to the psychological dimensions of text analysis. The researcher claims that cognitive psychology aims at exploring some of the symbolic dimensions of perception, comprehension, learning and memory. Besides, Beaugrande emphasizes the role of social psychology in the text analysis through saying that "social psychology is an intermediary study for bringing mental processes more fully into the scope of sociology proper and for widening the psychologists' concept of 'cognition' to incorporate attitudes, ideologies, emotions, and so on" (p.23). However, this study is very important because of its emphasis on the social dimensions in the text analysis and on the importance of style in analyzing text. Beaugrand says in this regard "style is a functional response to the cognitive and social organization of the context" (p.4).

Hatim (1997) has conducted a study that aims at studying the text in the light of context, text structure and texture. The study focuses on text typologies which are seen from the vantage point of modern text linguistics. Besides, it aims to test out both theoretical and practical insights in various domains of language in social life. It also sheds light on the role of socio-cultural dimensions in the text analysis. Hatim emphasizes the role of context in the text processing through saying that there are three contextual dimensions: "institutional-communicative" which is concerned with who is speaking to whom, "pragmatics" that deals with purpose of communication and "semiotics" which is governed by the kind of socio-cultural signs. However, the researcher focuses on the role of studying ideology in the text analysis, he defines it as " a body of ideas which reflects the beliefs and interests of an individual, a group of individuals, a societal institution, and which ultimately finds expression in language" (P.218).

Fairclough (1999) has tackled the theory of critical discourse analysis, which based on the study of text, discourse practice and socio-cultural practice. The researcher claims that language in texts always functions in the representation of experience and the world, in constituting social interaction between participants in discourse, and in tying parts of a text together into a coherent whole "a text". In fact, the study stems its importance from its concern with the relationship between language and ideology and between discourse and socio-cultural change. Besides, it also focuses on the textual analysis in the light of social and cultural change.

Van Dijk (2000) describes the cognitive discourse analysis from a theoretical point of view. He emphasizes the role of studying context to understand many aspects of discourse. Besides, Dijk claims that "cognitive" properties of the participants, such as their aims, beliefs, knowledge and opinions, are part of the studying of context. In this study, the researcher defines cognitive analysis as "an

analysis of those properties of discourse that are accounted for in terms of cognitive concepts, such as various types of mental representation" (p.6). Finally, this study attempts to study the role of cognitive analysis in discourse, its structures and its meaning.

Van Dijk (2001c) has described the role of knowledge in the theory of discourse. The researcher claims that knowledge has a vital role in the production and comprehension of text and talk. The study proposes any useful distinction between different types of knowledge and it shows how these types have different impact on discourse processing and structure. Van Dijk assures that knowledge is a property of its users and their communities, and language users need socio-cultural knowledge to produce and understand meaningful texts. Besides, Dijk thinks that an explicit theory of context is needed to explain how exactly the management of knowledge in discourse processing takes place.

2.5 theoretical frameworks - The Discourse Analysis Theory

The theoretical framework adopted by this study is the discourse analysis theory. This particular theory was purposely chosen as it is concerned with documenting the use of particular discursive devices for ideological purposes in contemporary societies. Also, it concerns with the interaction turns, paragraphs, written texts and the structure of whole conversations, such as audio, video-recordings, news etc. (Hammersley 2001).

METHODOLOGY

3.1 The Research Design

As far as a qualitative research is concerned, texts are analyzed for various purposes socially. The theoretical orientation of many qualitative research is that they are concerned more with process through which texts convey or portray 'reality' than with whether these texts or news true or false. According to Miles and Huberman (1994:10), the process of analysis is defined as "consisting of the current flow of activity: data reduction, data display and conclusion drawing/verification".

3.2 Sampling and Respondents

The aim of the research design in the present study is to take and conduct interview of five (5) Iraqi students studying in different subjects at University Utara Malaysia (UUM). Their opinion about news broadcasted by one news TV channel named Al Samaria and news circulated by one newspaper named Arab Times will be taken into consideration for the present study. The objective of this research design is to get different opinions of the five Iraqi students studying at University Utara Malaysia (UUM). The range of age of the respondents varies

between 25 and 30. The genders of interviewers are male. The students are all living near UUM dormitory and outside dormitory of UUM.

3.3 Method

Qualitative method will be employed for the purpose of the study. Simple random technique will be employed for the purpose of the study. As we know, in simple random sampling, the population has an equal and independent chance to be determined as a sample. Qualitative data will be collected from 5 (five) Iraqi students about their opinions about mass media in Iraq. The location of the interview is UUM campus, Sintok, Kedah, Malaysia.

3.4 Instruments

There are two kinds of instruments that will be used in this research. The first one is non-instrumental interview type, and the second one is based on open-ended questions. There are five questions given to the students to respond to and mention about their opinion. There is no right or wrong answer to any of those questions. The questions will examine the students on three personality traits. They are sensing/intuitive (S/N), thinking/feeling (T/F), and judging/perceiving (J/P).

3.5 Interview Questions

The interview questions ask about the opinions about news by the electronic media i.e. one news channel and news by the print media, i.e. one newspaper. The interview questions are given to five (5) Iraqi students studying in different disciplines at UUM. The interviewer explains the question in English as well as in Arabic to the students. The researcher makes every attempt to make the interviewers understand the questions, so he can get the exact answers he is looking for from them. Before conducting the interviews, the researcher explains about the interview to the respondents, and the message related to the interview. The interviews are conducted in different days, keeping the availability of the interviewers.

The open-ended questions about the newspaper and news TV channel are in the following:

- 1) Which one do you prefer to get the news from-a TV channel or a newspaper? Why?
- 2) How long do you stay following a TV or a newspaper?
- 3) To what extent do you think the newspapers are still important as TV?
- 4) Do you think the new generations will follow TV or newspapers or something else?
- 5) Which is more trusted to you a local media or an international media, such as BBC or CNN?

3.6 Data Analysis

In response to the question no 1, three respondents out five respondents agree that they prefer to get the news from TV as they get visual details, description and analysis of the news. As they are busy with their studies, they hardly get time to go through print media though they sometimes try to see the web version of the newspaper. As they are in abroad for the purpose of study, it is hard to get access to print media of the news. The rest of the respondents agree that they always prefer to get both news from TV channel as well as newspaper whenever they get time to go through both of the media.

Considering question no 2, half of the respondents opine that they do not get much time to follow either TV or newspaper news as they are quite far from their country, and they do not have access to print media all the time. The rest of respondents believe that they better stay close with electronic media more than print media. They prefer to talk to their family and friends via viber and we chat and get news about their country from their relatives. Those who are staying with their families cannot stay focused for a long time as they are frequently disturbed by their children and family who are eager to watch other programs.

In relation to question no 3, the majority of the respondents agree that it is still relevant to read news at newspapers though watching TV news is sometimes preferable because of lack of time. After watching news on TV, the respondents still feel that they are not fully satisfied, and they still need to read the print media. So, the appeal of newspaper is not diminishing day by day whether in Arab or other part of the world.

With the mention of question no 4, except one, all of them feel and believe that new generation will not have the same urgency like them (present generation). The new generation will not follow print media very much. They will depend on electronic media, like TV news or face book or twitter, or other social media. One respondent mentions this that new generation will make some time out of their busy schedule and read print media newspaper.

Responding to the last question, half of the respondents mention that both local media and international media are biased. They do not trust them very much as they always get one side of the story. The other side is not covered up at all; they do not present neutral story. The rest of them mention that local media gives biased news whereas the international media more or less give news which can be believable.

3.7 Findings

This study deals basically with the social dimensions of the media language of Iraq. It also aims at drawing a distinction between English and Arabic newspaper's editorial. Besides, this study focuses on the study of English and Arabic news broadcasts from a social point of view through contrastive analysis for these news broadcasts.

It is observed through the primary survey conducted for the purpose of this study that media language in Iraq is characterized by the social dimension which reveals its linguistic power. However, it is noticed that the social dimension of the media language of Iraq has not been seriously tackled or treated. Thus, the present research tries to analyze and discuss this dimension that characterizes the media language in Iraq.

The researcher has discussed about The Arab Times and the television English and Arabic news broadcasts each one with the other, on the basis of social linguistic analysis. These editorials and news broadcasts have undergone a linguistic analysis from a social point of view. Besides, the researcher has focused on the social dimension of both English and Arabic editorial and English and Arabic news broadcasts, taking into account to whom the writer directs his speech and how he reflects his psyche through his style.

So, the researcher has applied the social linguistic analysis through a contrastive method for the newspaper editorials and the news broadcasts, and also the theory of discourse analysis which has been very useful in this regard.

CONCLUSION

The social aspects of a language is very important as human language is used to communicate between individuals in society. Human language has a social message which is conveyed through media; depending on the context the language is used. The main concern of this paper is to study media language and its linguistics power which have been studied successfully from sociological perspectives. The message given by media language has a social role that shows cases the writer's opinion towards certain issues. The present study is able to explore those two aspects of the media language used by English and Arabic news, and also English and Arabic news broadcast in Iraq, and the media discourse is able to study this dimension in order to find out its influence in shaping the media language of Iraq.

The present study has successfully discussed and analyzed the English and Arabic newspaper and the English and Arabic news broadcast through a contrastive analysis with the social dimension in it. Discourse analysis theory has worked as an able framework under qualitative method. The study also has successfully drawn a distinction between English and Arabic newspaper in Iraq. The primary conducted survey of the paper has given the result that media language in Iraq is characterized by the social dimension which reveals its linguistic power. One of the significant findings of this paper is that the social dimension of the media language of Iraq has not been seriously tackled or treated.

Another finding is that the present paper takes into account of the writers' direction of speech, and it reflects their opinions through the style used,

considering the social dimension of both English and Arabic news and English and Arabic news broadcasts.

The findings of the present study are mixed one if we take into consideration of the opinions of 5 (five) Iraqi students studying in different disciplines at UUM. Many of the students prefer both TV news as well as newspapers regarding the news of Iraq. They are more concerned about the news happening in Iraq. Many of them are worried about the prospect of reading newspapers by the new generation. They think that the new generation will not read the newspaper as they like to do. In the interview taken, the majority of the students think that the news broadcasted by BBC, CNN or like are more reliable and the local media is biased in disseminating news to the audience as the government thinks about their own interest in politics. The local media in Iraq whether electronic media or print media to greater extent represent the voice of the incumbent government.

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Appendix A

- 1) Which one do you prefer to get the news from—a TV channel or a newspaper? Why?
- 2) How long do you stay following a TV or a newspaper?
- 3) To what extent do you think the newspapers are still important as TV?
- 4) Do you think the new generations will follow TV or newspapers or something else?
- 5) Which is more trusted to you—a local media or an international media, such as BBC or CNN?